

The Chemistry of Natural Products. Part I. Chemical Studies on Erythroplamic Acid

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Degradative experiments support structure (I) for erythroplamic acid.

Erythroplamic acid is a diterpene acid related to other diterpenoids isolated from the bark of *Erythrophleum guineense* G. Don. It occurs as an ester of *N,N*-dimethylamino-ethanol, the resulting base being known as erythroplamine (Engel *et al.*, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1950, **69**, 396). Erythroplamic acid contains one double bond $\alpha\beta$ to the carboxyl group, one keto group, one hydroxyl group, and a sterically hindered methoxycarbonyl group (Mathieson *et al.*, *Exper.*, 1960, **16**, 404). The structure of this acid has been shown to be (I) on the basis of its conversion to $3\beta, 7\beta$ -dihydroxycassanic acid (II) (Arya and Engel, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, in press). This communication deals with some chemical studies on erythroplamic acid carried out prior to the complete elucidation of its structure (Arya, Ph. D. Thesis, London University, 1959, pp. 171-181).

Erythroplamic acid exhibited infrared bands at 3540, 1710, 1680, and 1640 cm^{-1} . These bands are characteristic, respectively, of a hydroxyl group, a methoxycarbonyl group superimposed on a six-membered ring carbonyl, a carboxyl group of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated acid, and the double bond of this group. Treatment of erythroplamic acid in methanol with ethereal diazomethane gave methyl erythroplamate. The infrared spectrum of this compound in bromoform solution showed bands at 3520 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl, 3580 cm^{-1} in CCl_4), 1705 cm^{-1} (methoxycarbonyl groups superimposed on a six-membered ring carbonyl, 1710 cm^{-1} in CCl_4), and at 1650 cm^{-1} (double bond of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ester). Methyl erythroplamate formed a mono-acetate. The infrared spectrum of methyl erythroplamate in carbon tetrachloride solution had bands at 1740, 1240 cm^{-1} (acetate), 1725 cm^{-1} (carbomethoxyl groups superimposed on a six-membered ring carbonyl), and at 1650 cm^{-1} (double bond of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ester).

When methyl erythroplamate was oxidised with chromic anhydride in acetic acid, it formed methyl dehydroerythroplamate (III), $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6$. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum of this compound was typical of an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ester (λ_{max} 221 $\text{m}\mu$; $\log \epsilon$ 4.27). The infrared spectrum supported this view and showed bands in chloroform solution at 1710 and 1650 cm^{-1} . Methyl dehydroerythroplamate gave a positive Zimmermann test indicating the presence of a 3-oxo grouping (Barton and Mayo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 887).

Sodium borohydride reduced erythroplamic acid to a dihydroxy acid (IV), $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6$, in which the conjugated double bond was still present (λ_{max} 219 $\text{m}\mu$; $\log \epsilon$ 4.21). A Zerewitinoff estimation in a mixture of *N*-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline and di-

isoamyl ether as solvent indicated the presence of three active hydrogens (for method of estimation, see Perold and Snyman, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1958, 225).

Ozonolysis of erythroplamic acid or methylerythroplamate at -50° to -70° in chloroform solution afforded a hydroxydiketone (Va: R=H), $C_{19}H_{28}O_5$. The infrared absorption spectrum of this compound showed strong bands at 3500 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl) and 1712 cm^{-1} (methoxycarbonyl group superimposed on two cyclohexanone type carbonyls). Similarly ozonolysis of methyl erythroplamate acetate yielded an acetoxydiketone (Vb: R=Ac), $C_{21}H_{30}O_5$. Oxalic acid was also obtained in about 20% yield. The isolation of the latter confirms the nature of the side-chain which is the same as in cassaic acid (Arya and Mathieson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3623). The diketone (Vb) formed a bis-2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. Mild alkaline hydrolysis of (Vb) furnished the hydroxydiketone (Va) (mixed m.p. showing no depression).

The Wolff-Kishner reduction of the hydroxydiketone (Va) under strictly anhydrous conditions (Barton *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2056) afforded a crystalline hydroxy-acid (VI) in a small quantity. Concomitant hydrolysis of the sterically hindered methoxycarbonyl group took place. These results together with spectral evidence support the structure (I) for erythroplamic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. Optical rotations and ultraviolet absorption spectra were determined in 95% ethanol, unless otherwise stated. Light petroleum refers to the fraction of petroleum having the boiling range of $40-60^{\circ}$.

Erythrophlamic Acid (I).—Methyl erythrophlamate (40 mg.) in 2*N* ethanolic KOH solution (5 c.c.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hrs. The solution was cooled to 0° and acidified with 2*N*-HCl (7.5 c.c.), when crystals appeared. These were collected, dried, and weighed. It (35 mg.) was recrystallised from methanol-water, m.p. 218-20°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -62^\circ$ ($c=1$) (Lit. cites m. p. 218-20°). UV spectrum: $\lambda_{\max}$ 223 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$ 4.20. IR spectrum (in nujol mull): strong bands at 3540, 1710, 1680, 1640 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 66.43; H, 7.77; O, 25.73; OMe, 8.67. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6$: C, 66.64; H 7.99; O, 25.37; OMe, 8.20%).

Methyl Erythrophlamate.—Erythrophlamic acid (10 mg.) in methanol (2 c.c.) was treated with an excess of ethereal diazomethane. On working up in the usual manner, a crystalline residue (9.9 mg.) was obtained which crystallised from methanol-ether, m.p. 175-76°, $[\alpha]_D^{21} = -67^\circ$ ($c=0.5$) (Lit. cites m.p. 177°). (Found: C, 67.42.; H, 7.99; OMe, 16.11. Calc. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6$: C, 67.32; H, 8.22; OMe 15.86%).

UV spectrum: $\lambda_{\max}$ 223 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$ 4.30. IR spectrum (in CHBr_3 solution): strong bands at 3540, 1705, 1650 cm^{-1} . (in CCl_4 solution), strong bands at 3580, 1710, 1650 cm^{-1} .

Treatment of the ester in *N*-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline with excess of methylmagnesium iodide in di-isoamyl ether gave methane equivalent to 0.94 active hydrogen.

Methyl Erythrophlamate Acetate.—Methyl erythrophlamate (80 mg.) in anhydrous pyridine (5 c.c.) and acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) were warmed on a steam bath for 1 hr. and left at room temperature overnight. When the reaction mixture was worked up in the usual manner, a gummy acetate (86 mg.) resulted. It was twice sublimed in high vacuum (2×10^{-5} mm) at 170°. The sublimate crystallised from ether, m. p. 171°, $[\alpha]_D^{22} -59^\circ$ ($c=1$, CHCl_3) (Lit. cites m.p. 173°). (Found: C, 65.18; H 7.90; COMe, 10.5. Calc for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_7$: C, 65.38; H, 8.11; $-\text{COCH}_3$, 9.9%).

UV spectrum: $\lambda_{\max}$ 223 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$ 4.21. IR spectrum (in CCl_4 solution): strong bands at 1740, 1725, 1650, and 1240 cm^{-1} . No methane was evolved on treatment with methylmagnesium iodide in di-isoamyl ether.

Methyl Dehydroerythrophlamate (III).—Methyl erythrophlamate (80 mg.) in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added to a suspension of chromic anhydride (20 mg.) in acetic acid (5 c.c.) at 45°. The reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature overnight. It was then poured into water and extracted with ether; on working up in the usual manner it gave a crystalline residue (77 mg.) This was crystallised first from petroleum (60-80°) and then twice from ether-light petroleum, m.p. 133-34°, $[\alpha]_D -101^\circ$ ($c=1$). (Found: C, 67.57; H, 7.93; O, 24.58; OMe, 15.81. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6$ requires. C, 67.66; H, 7.75; O, 24.59; OMe, 15.90%).

UV spectrum: $\lambda_{\max}$ 221 m μ ; $\log \epsilon$ 4.27. IR spectrum (in CHCl_3 solution): strong bands at 1710, 1650 cm^{-1} . This compound gave positive tetranitromethane, Zimmermann, and Liebermann-Burchard tests. Methane was not evolved on treatment with methylmagnesium iodide in di-isoamyl ether.

Sodium Borohydride Reduction of Erythrophlamic Acid.—Erythrophlamic acid (10.2 mg.) in absolute methanol (3 c.c.) was treated with sodium borohydride (5.1 mg.) in water

(0.8 c.c.). On working up in the usual manner it gave a crystalline residue, m.p. 235-38°, which was recrystallised from methanol to furnish the pure *dihydroxy acid* (IV), m.p. 273-74°. UV spectrum: $\lambda_{\max}$ 219 m μ ; log ϵ 4.21. (Found: C, 66.21; H, 8.32. C₂₁H₃₂O₆ requires C, 66.21; H 8.48%).

Treatment of the dihydroxy-acid in *N*-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline with excess of methylmagnesium iodide in di-isoamyl ether gave methane equivalent to 3 active hydrogens.

Ozonolysis of Methyl Erythrophlamate.—Methyl erythrophlamate (37 mg.) in dry chloroform (20 c.c.) was ozonised with an oxygen-ozone mixture (19:1) for 30 mins. at -50° to -70°. The bluish ozonide solution was allowed to warm to room temperature, then evaporated to dryness at the steam bath under reduced pressure.

The gummy ozonide was shaken with zinc powder (500 mg.), glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and water (5 c.c.) for 2 hrs. Unchanged metal was filtered and the filtrate worked up in the usual manner to give a crystalline residue (21 mg.). Three recrystallisations from ether—light petroleum gave colorless needles of the *hydroxydiketone* (Va), m.p. 211-12°. (Found: C, 67.95; H, 8.10. C₁₉H₂₈O₅ requires C, 67.82; H, 8.38%). IR spectrum (in CHCl₃ solution): 3500, 1712 cm⁻¹.

This compound gave a positive Zimmermann test. When erythrophlamic acid (20 mg.) was ozonised under identical conditions, it furnished the same hydroxydiketone (Va) (12 mg.) (superimposable IR spectra).

Ozonolysis of Methyl Erythrophlamate Acetate.—Methyl erythrophlamate acetate (30 mg.) in chloroform (30 c.c.) was ozonised for 30 mins. at -50° to -70°. The bluish ozonide solution was worked up in the manner described above to furnish a gummy residue (21 mg.). This was crystallised three times from ether—light petroleum to furnish the needles of the *acetoxydiketone* (Vb), m.p. 182-83°. IR spectrum (in CHCl₃ solution): Strong bands at 1740, 1715, 1240 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 66.97; H, 7.79; O, 24.87. C₂₁H₃₀O₆ requires C, 66.64; H, 7.99; and O, 25.37%).

The acetoxydiketone (Vb) formed a *bis-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* in orange needles from ethyl acetate—ethanol, m.p. 271° (decomp.). UV spectrum: $\lambda_{\max}$ 360 m μ ; log ϵ 4.59 (CHCl₃). (Found: N, 14.37. C₃₃H₃₈O₁₂N₈ requires N, 14.83%).

Isolation of Oxalic Acid from the Ozonolysis Products of Methyl Erythrophlamate Acetate.—The acidic fraction from the above ozonolysis was saponified with 2*N*-NaOH, cooled to room temperature, and acidified with 2*N*-HCl. The acidified solution was extracted with ether in a liquid/liquid extractor for 3 days. On working up the resulting ethereal extract, a brown gum (16 mg.) was obtained. This was sublimed three times at 180°/0.1 mm and the sublimate (6 mg.) had m.p. 187-89°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of oxalic acid, 187-89°.

Hydrolysis of the Acetoxydiketone (Vb).—The acetoxydiketone (Vb) (5mg.) in absolute ethanol (5 c.c.) and 2*N*-KOH (3 drops) was boiled under reflux for 2 hrs. and worked up in the usual manner to give a gum (3 mg.). This product, after two crystallisations gave colorless needles, m.p. 210.5-12°. The mixed m.p. with the hydroxydiketone (Va) was undepressed.

Wolff-Kishner Reduction of Hydroxydiketone (Va).—The hydroxydiketone (Va) (40 mg.) was refluxed for 48 hours at 210° with redistilled diethyleneglycol (10 c.c.), sodium (20 mg.), and an excess of anhydrous hydrazine. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and worked up in the usual way. A brown gummy residue (28 mg.) resulted, which was treated with charcoal in methanol and filtered through a column of silica gel (2 g.) using chloroform as the solvent. It was obtained as a colorless gum which crystallised very slowly to give fine needles of the *hydroxy-acid* (VI), m.p. 231–32°. IR spectrum (in CHCl₃ solution): 3500, 1670 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 73.10; H, 10.19. C₁₈H₃₀O₃ requires C, 73.43; H, 10.27%).

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